

ENGINEERING COMPOSITE ELECTRE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: Modification of polymer materials by electric fields is now part of advanced materials science. Polymer electrets are efficient means of rising serviceability of joints with small clearances between conjugated parts. Electret field makes it possible to regulate wetting and spreading, sorption and diffusion, as well as capillary permeation of liquids. Electrets in machines protect metal-polymer joints against corrosion, increase adhesion of composite components and articles, improve strength, enhance technological effectiveness of composite formation, improve tribological characteristics of friction joints. Electret plastics bear mechanical loads in machines and are the source of electric field. Electrets as materials of a new generation respond to the latest trends in technology for simultaneous increase in serviceability and reduction in machine size and mass.

KEYWORDS: electrets and materials, polarization, metal-polymer electrets, wetting and spreading, strength and adhesion, corrosion protection, tribological characteristics

INTRODUCTION

Electric polarization is intrinsic physical state of the polymers being dielectrics in their majority. Polarization-retaining dielectrics, i.e. electrets or electric analogues of magnets are characterized by ability to generate a constant electric field.

The electrets are traditionally used in gas filters, microphones, systems of electronic focusing [1]. Electrets were not used in joints contributing much into machine serviceability, including bearings, seals, anti-corrosion systems. Nevertheless, experience in different technologies showed that electrets could improve working capacity of machine joints with a small clearance between conjugated parts [2,3]. The processes of lubrication, capillary permeation, spread of liquids, etc. (where surface phenomena are very important) can be controlled using a relatively weak electret field.

Technologists are usually not paying attention to the fact that electric fields always generate polarization in dielectrics. Polarization emerges even when electric field is used to solve some mechanical or physic-chemical problems to match dielectric components at composites forming.

More attention has been recently paid to ecological, environment protection problems. The problems arise from the growing industry, which environmental effect is commensurable with the natural processes. The former leads to changes in water, soil, air, violates equilibrium in nature. Application of electrets can influence some aspects of the problem. Use of electric field source in machines is ecologically pure. An experience has been attained in efficient

purification of industrial wastes and ejections, rise of combustion effectiveness, reduction of hostile media leakage by transfer of materials into the electret state.

Electrets perform two functions in machines: 1. the mechanical load carrier and 2. electric field source. Their application responds to the recent technological trends and permits to rise serviceability, reduce dimensions and material consumption in machines. These materials are fairly competitive, their composition and technology are new and patented.

The object of the present paper is to describe new perspectives of electret composite materials production and efficient use in machine joints governing serviceability of equipment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Polarization Methods

Methods of polymer composite electric polarization realize mostly the technology of thermo- and corona-electrets. In principle, they can be performed at any stage of article production [4].

It has been found out that polymer composites can be polarized by charged fillers [5]. Polyvinylbutyral (PVB) impregnation with corona-discharged oxide powders results in a maximal characteristic of the electret charge (Fig.1) during thermally stimulated depolarization (TSD) of the filled films. Space charge of the film and sheet materials can be formed without sources of electric voltage.

It has been shown earlier that a stable electret state emerges when the polymer layer between short-circuited electrodes of unlike metals in “metal 1-polymer-metal 2” systems undergoes thermal treatment [2,6-8]. The new type of electret state was called metal-polymer electret (MPE). It has also been established that during their formation and operation MPE can display and realize functional potentialities of composites, in particular, strength, corrosion resistance, as well as frictional, electric and other characteristics [9].

The use of fillers influences electric polarization of polymer composites. PVB samples were thermally treated under 393 K in contact with short-circuited copper and aluminum electrodes. Due to conductive or electret fillers graphs (Fig. 2) fall into two groups. The first group fillers (curves 1-3) features high charge density (up to 10^{-3} C/cm²). The conducting filler particle bears, presumably, the function of auxiliary electrodes at polarization and the amount of charge carriers transmitted from the electrode into polymer matrix increases too. The second group (4,5) is characterized by the drop of charge with increasing content of dielectric filler. The latter does not participate in electric conductivity at sample polarization. The degree polarization current and TSD charge decrease with increase of filling degree.

The dependencies (Fig. 2) have a maximum at about 1 mass% of the filler content. Small quantities of foreign impurities contribute to formation of a more perfect permolecular structure in polymer binders and to electret charge formation. Further increase in filling degree causes disordering of permolecular structures accompanied by TSD charge reduction.

When $C > 1\%$ (1-3) the charge grows and then reduces due to reduced quantity of polarized polymer. The described process is most prominent when the sample is filled with dielectrics (4,5).

Wetting and Spreading

Liquid wetting and spreading over polymer surface can be regulated by the latter polarizing.

Pentaplast (PPI) films were transferred into electret state by heating between steel electrodes under $150\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and electric field of $E = 10^4\text{-}10^6\text{ V/m}$ (thermo-electrets) during 1 h or by corona discharge (corona-electrets). The technique of measuring liquid spreading over the sample surface is described in [10].

Fig. 1. TSD currents in SiO_2 -filled PVB (up to 20 mass%) versus temperature and filler charge: 1 - corona-discharged, 2 - original

Fig. 2. TSD charge density in PVB samples depending on filler content: 1 — carbon fabric, 3 — Al and Cu powders, 4 — basalt fiber, 5 — fiber glass

The increase of sample polarization and electret charge reduces the initial velocity of the liquid spread (Table 1) and the actual contact area between the drop and sample (Fig. 3). The polarizing charge creates energy barrier in experimental conditions. To overcome this barrier the motive force of spreading is spent.

Fig. 3. Increase in diethylene glycole drop radius Δr spreading over pentaplast sample surface as related to time t when the drop was placed on the sample and electret charge density (C/m^2): 1 - 0, 2 - 10^{-5} , 3 - 0.003, 4 - 0.36, 5 - 0.58. $\Delta r = r - r_0$, where r and r_0 are the radius in moments t and 0.

Table 1. The initial velocity v of DEG spreading over PPI versus sample surface charge density σ .

Sample	$\sigma, C/m^2$	$v, 10^{-4} \text{ mm/sec}$
Reference	0	2.8
Thermo-electret	$4.96 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1.4
	$2.78 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.6
Corona-electret	0.36	0.4

The experimental dependence of edge wetting angle on the polarizing charge density is described by the Eqn 1:

$$\cos \Theta = \cos \Theta_0 - 1.4 \cdot 10^4 \sigma - 2 \cdot 10^{-9} \sigma^2 \quad (1)$$

where Θ and Θ_0 are the liquid equilibrium edge wetting angles for, correspondingly, electret and nonpolarized samples; σ is the sample surface charge density.

Figure 4 shows the scheme for a device to investigate capillary motion of a liquid in contact gaps between steel sample 7 and polymer electret coating 6 on the substrate 4. The liquid flows over to the studied joint from a glass tube 1 where its level reduces by a value Δh . Capillary pressure of the liquid penetrated into the joint and that of the column of the height Δh in tube 1 are equal. Based on the above procedure an Eqn 2 has been derived [3]

$$\Delta h = \frac{2}{dS\rho g} - \frac{W - \sigma_{12}}{\cos \Theta} \quad (2)$$

where S is tube 1 cross section, ρ - liquid density, g - gravity force acceleration, W is the work to be spent for the liquid to separate from the coating, σ_{12} - surface tension at the liquid gas surface.

Fig. 4. Measurement diagram (a) of liquid capillary permeation into clearance between solids and dependence (b) of liquid level Δh variation in measured capillary on the sample charge surface density σ : a) 1 - glass tube, 2 - water, 3 - connecting tube, 4 - substrate, 5 - conduit, 6 - coating, 7 - sample, 8 - punch in the coating; b) 1 - polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA), 2 - fluoroplast-3 (F-3).

Nonmonotonous character of curves 1 and 2 in Fig. 4 is the result of superimposed reduction velocities W and $\cos \Theta$ when the electret charge grows. On the initial inclining portion of the curves, the reduction of W dominates. At the same time physical adsorption of liquid molecules is intensified, which rises the double electric layer on the electret surface. When the layer is fully formed, W values stabilize. This corresponds to the minimum of $\Delta h = f(\sigma)$ dependence. The ascending portion of the curves is the result of $\cos \Theta$ reduction under constant W .

Curves 1 and 2 correspond to difference in parameters of PMMA and hydrophobic F-3 wetting with water.

Sorption and Diffusion

The theory of diffusion based on the mechanism of diffusing particles jumping over the solid vacancies [11] suggests the following Eqn 3:

$$D = \frac{a^2}{\tau_0} \exp(-W / kT) \quad (3)$$

where D is diffusion coefficient, a is the solid lattice constant, τ about 10^{-13} s is the particle oscillation period, W - energy of diffusion activation, k - gas constant, T - absolute temperature. If diffusion proceeds in a solid dielectric possessing a polarized charge, then $W = U + E + E_e$, where U is the energy of vacancy formation, E is energy barrier height, E_e - energy acquired by a particle in the electret field. Diffusion proceeds in the electret faster or slower as compared to the polarized dielectric depending on E_e sign.

The polarized charge influences first of all the diffusing substance sorption by the electret. This influence behavior is conditioned by formation of the double electric layer in vicinity of

the electret surface. Sorption of organic solvent vapors was studied using PVB films thermally treated in contact with shorted copper and aluminum electrodes. The sample polarized charge density determined by the TSD method was about 10^{-5} C/cm². Both polarized and reference (thermally treated in contact with aluminum electrodes) samples were endured in diethylene glycole (DEG) and benzene vapors under $T_1 = 303$ K and $T_2 = 323$ K (T_2 is about T_C of PVB). The experimental technique is described in [12].

Fig. 5. Mass (M) of PVB samples versus endurance time (t) in DEG vapors. Temperature, K: 1, 2 -323, 3, 4 - 303. Samples: 1, 3 - reference, 2 and 4 - electret.

In Fig. 5 it is seen that DEG sorption by the electret under T_2 (curve 2) is much less than in [1]. When $T_1 < T_c$ the difference in sorption is not large (3 and 4). The similar results were obtained for the samples treated in benzene vapors (Table 2).

Table 2. Increase of PVB sample mass (M) depending on time (t) of endurance in benzene vapors under 323 K.

$t, 10^3$ s	M, 10 ⁻² g for the samples	
	reference	electret
4.5	0.55	0
6.4	1.10	0
7.3	1.30	0.01
10.7	1.50	0.05
13.9	1.66	0.14
15.2	1.73	0.24

When $T < T_c$, the reduction in segmental mobility of macromolecules bounds sorption due to lower velocity of conformation transformations. This probably levels the difference in sorption of solvent vapors by electret and nonelectret films (curves 3 and 4 in Fig. 5). Upon the formation of the double electric layer from oriented dipoles near the electret surface, an equilibrium concentration of the solvent is established in the sample. The film permolecular structure in the process of electric polarization spurs sorption reduction in both polar (DEG) and nonpolar (molecular dipole moment equals zero) solvents. It appears that benzene

nonpolar molecules acquire the dipole moment in the electret field and interact with the electret following the described mechanism. Difference in DEG and benzene diffusion is attributed to DEG stronger solution capacity as compared to PVB.

Adhesion

The effect of polarized charge on polymer adhesion to metals was first studied in the metal-polymer-metal systems [13]. Strength of splice adhesion was determined by lamination method. Strength increased 1.5-2 times when the adhesive joint formation was accompanied with the polymer transformation into MPE. Adhesion increase is much effected by activated in electric field diffusion of the metal-polymer contact reaction products into the polymer.

A model of a composite material is suggested. The composite incorporates a thermoplastic polymer binder and dispersed particles of metal oxides which differ by the value of the standard electrochemical potentials [14]. Fuming-oxides (FO) were used as the filler. They are a by-product of lead-zinc production and contain Zn, Pb, Mg, Cu and other oxides. During material formation FO reduction to metals is proceeding. The reduction of the sample ohmic resistance at heating, as well as the results of X-ray diffraction analysis are the proof of it. It was observed that with increasing time of treatment the intensity of peaks characterizing the oxide crystalline structure reduced, while the intensity of peaks corresponding to pure metal increased.

When a certain concentration of the conducting filler is reached, the formation of conducting bridges is probable in the composite and the contact between particles is unnecessary for the polarizing current to run. Microcircuits metal 1-polymer-metal 2 are formed between both the filler particles in the polymer matrix bulk and between a separate particle and metal electrode contacting the sample. Thus, electrochemical interaction of the composite components is realized in the process of thermal treatment which increases adhesion (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Strength of adhesive joints (a) and protective capability (corrosion rate, b) from FO containing polymer composites with Al foil versus FO content and filler type: 1 - PE, 2 - PVB, 3 - PPI.

Rearrangement in the polymer permolecular structure accompanying polarization causes, as a rule, improvement of their strength and impairment of deformation characteristics. So, thermally electrified polycarbonate and PTFE samples show an increased by 15-60% breaking tensile stress and several times relaxation time of mechanical stress [4].

Strengthening of polymer composites by transferring their components into electret state has been verified experimentally [5]. Breaking tensile stress of composites (PE, PA, PVC, PPI, PTFE matrices; reinforcing elements - basalt, phenylone, glass, Dacron fibers) increases 1.6-2.5 times due to filler and matrix electric polarization. Adhesion of polymer binder to filler exerts a substantial effect on composite strength. Force of fiber glass peeling off from PVC-based fiber glass plastic increases at binder polarization from 3.4 to 4.4. kN/m. For PPI it increases from 1.7 to 2.6. kN/m .

Protection against Corrosion

One of crucial factors for the polymer-based rustproof systems is the barrier action of polymer elements insulating metal from environment. It is believed that, when a structural polymer barrier is disturbed, it does not influence metal corrosion in electrolytes. Nevertheless, the polymer electret field effect on both barrier characteristics of polymers and kinetics of electrochemical processes in metal-polymer systems should be taken into account. The polarized charge effects the kinetics of liquid spreading over polymer electrets and sorption of liquid media.

Diffusion of liquids into MPE coating g on metals has been studied. If liquid concentration C_0 on the coating surface is supposed to be constant during diffusion, then the amount of liquid sorbed by MPE to the moment t is [15]

$$Q = \frac{2C_0}{\pi} \sqrt{Dt} \exp(-\alpha\sigma) \quad (4)$$

where D diffusion coefficient of nonpolarized polymer; σ -MPE surface charge density determined by TSD. The parameter $\alpha \sim 3 \cdot 10^4$ is determined experimentally for each polymer-liquid combination. The equation describes satisfactorily diffusion into MPE with $\sigma > 5 \cdot 10^{-7}$ C/cm². Probable reduction of coating diffusion permeability using polarization is limited by the ultimate charge density of MPE $\sigma \leq 10^{-5}$ C/cm² due to electrodes blocked by products of metal-polymer reaction [16].

The initial corrosion of protected by polymer coating metal is penetration of corrosive medium along the coating-metal interface leading to the coating peeling off. Peeling is accompanied by the electrode metal potential bias to the negative domain. This evidences that under the coating there occurs either retardation of cathodic oxidation or acceleration of metal ionization. Both processes can be controlled using electret coatings.

Table 3 demonstrates test results of polymer coatings on steel with a through punch in the protecting film reaching the substrate. Coatings of group A were formed following the classical vibro-vortex method. Melting of group B coatings was accomplished in electric field of $E = 20$ kV/cm strength by connecting upper electrode with the positive pole of a high-voltage source and the substrate with the ground. When melting group C coatings, the polymer layer was covered by a copper foil closed in the steel substrate. After cooling the foil was peeled off.

Table 3. The coating peeling area S and change of the substrate electrode potential ΔU depending on endurance time t in a strong NaCl solution.

Coating Group	Coating material	S (cm ²) during t (days)					ΔU (V) 5 days
		1 day	2	3	4	5	
A	PPI	0.25	0.74	2.03	2.76	3.97	0.24
	PVB	3.03	6.24	10.32	—	—	—
B	PPI	0	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.04	0
	PVB	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.07	0.08	0.02
C	PPI	0	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.03	0
	PVB	0.01	0.02	0.05	0.07	0.08	0.02

It is obvious that Group B thermo-electrets which contact the substrate by the negatively charged surface peel off slower and their substrate unrefining is less as compared to nonelectret ones (group A). Similar results showed MPE-based coatings (C) formed without outer electric source.

Triboengineering Characteristics

Among phenomena accompanying polymer friction, those of electrical nature are the least studied, though their influence is not of minor importance.

Crucial factors governing friction and wear of polymers being either a polarized body or electric field source are the following. Electrization potential U of the polymer element in a metal-polymer friction pair succeeds to saturate rather quickly (in a few seconds). Change of U sign during initial friction can be attributed to loss of moisture by the element surface layers. Air humidity and the presence of a liquid film on the friction surface exerts a considerable effect on U . Polymer in the field of electrization charge transfers under frictional heating into tribological electret state [7]. It determines the kinetics and intensity of physico-chemical processes in the friction zone. Most important experimentally recorded parameters of triboelectret state are the efficient surface density of charge q and TSD current spectrum. The latter helps to estimate the correlation between homo- and heterocharge in the triboelectret, as well as activation energy of the charge formation and declining, time of relaxation, etc.

MPE wear was examined by removing from the friction surface the layers which contacted during polarization Cu and Al electrodes. The experimental technique is described in [18]. MPE charge is concentrated mainly in the surface layer (20-60 μm). It was recorded by TSD that q near the copper electrode is higher than near the aluminum one. Wear of the friction surface contacted Al at polarization is lower than that contacted Cu (Fig. 7). Obviously MPE wear proceeds more intensively with q growth. Such a regularity is violated only with thin (15-20 μm) surface layers displaying elevated concentration of chemical structural defects. This is also typical, though to a less degree, of nonelectret samples.

Fig. 7: The dependence of MPE wear rate on the thickness of the layer removed from the sample surface contacting Al (1) and Cu (2) at polarization. 3 - reference sample. Sample materials: a - PVB, b - PPI, c - PA.

Variation of MPE tribological characteristics are due to space charge formation accompanied by structural rearrangement of the near-electrode layer. Rise in degree of nonpolarized PPI samples crystallinity constitutes 4% from the copper electrode side and 6% from the aluminum one. Upon removal of 80-100 μm thick layer the polarized and nonpolarized samples do not differ in crystallinity degree. It may be so that space charge generated in the near-electrode regions during crystallization hamper macromolecule packing. Therefore, the larger charge value localized near copper electrode corresponds to a smaller degree of crystallinity.

Novel triboengineering materials and friction joints have been developed [19-20]. They incorporate MPE as electric field generator to improve friction and wear parameters.

CONCLUSIONS

Polymer electrets are used to regulate technological processes of composite material formation. They involve sorption, diffusion, wetting, spreading, saturation and etc. Electret composites contribute to protecting machine parts against corrosion, raise of components adhesion, material hardening and improvement of friction joint tribological characteristics.

Electret composites are the new materials effecting the engineering developments.

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REFERENCES

1. Electrets, Ed. by Sessler G.M., Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1987.
2. Goldade V.A. and Pinchuk L.S., Electret Plastics: Physics and Materials Science, Nauka i Tekhnika, Minsk, 1987.
3. Pinchuk L.S., Hermetology, Nauka i Tekhnika, Minsk, 1992.
4. Voronezhnev Yu. I., Goldade V.A., Pinchuk L.S. and Snezhkov V.V., Electric and Magnetic Fields in Technology of Polymer Composites, Nauka i Tekhnika, Minsk, 1990.
5. Vertyachikh I.M., The Development of Engineering Polymer Composite Materials with Electret Components, Ph.D. Thesis, Gomel, 1990.
6. Goldade V.A., Pinchuk L.S. and Voronezhnev Yu.I., Electric Polarization of Polymers in Metal-Dielectric- Metal Systems, Proc. ISE-6 Conf., IEEE, New York, 1988, pp.419-423.
7. Goldade V.A., Voronezhnev Yu.I. and Pinchuk L.S., On Mechanism of Polymer Polarization in Metal 1-Polymer- Metal 2 Systems, Proc. Intern. Conf. Plastko- 90, Ostrava, 1990, pp. 76-80.
8. Goldade V.A. and Pinchuk L.S., New technology of Electrically Polarized Polymers Creation during Heat Treatment in Contact with Different Metals, Proc. Polymer Process. Soc., Stuttgart, 1995, pp. 6-9.
9. Goldade V.A. and Pinchuk L.S., New Spheres of Metal- Polymer Electrets Technical Application, Proc. ISE-9, IEEE, Shanghai, 1996, pp. 1079-1080.
10. Plevachuk V.G., Vertyachikh I.M., Goldade V.A. and Pinchuk L.S., Effect of the Charge of a Polymer Electret on the Spreading of Liquids, Polymer Science, A, Vol. 37, No. 10, pp. 1071-1074.
11. Frenkel Ya. I., Kinetic Theory of Liquids, USSR Acad. of Sci., Moscow, 1945.
12. Vertyachikh I.M., Goldade V.A., Neverov A.S. and Pinchuk L.S., The Effect of Polymer Electret Electric Field on Sorption of Organic Solvent Vapors, High-Mol. Comp., 1982, Vol. 24B, No. 9, pp. 683-687.
13. Belyi V.A., Goldade V.A., Neverov A.S. and Pinchuk L.S., Polymer Strength in Splices of Unlike Metals, Polymer Mechanics, 1977, No. 4, pp. 740-742.
14. Goldade V.A., On Adhesive Strength and Protective Capacity of Polymer Composite Coatings, Mechanics of Composite Materials, 1981, No. 5, pp. 842-845.
15. Voronezhnev Yu.I., Effect of Polymer Coating Electric Polarization on its Diffusion Permeability, Trans. of BSSR Acad. of Sci., Phys. Techn. Sci., 1986, No.4, pp. 42-44.
16. Goldade V.A., Voronezhnev Yu. I. and Pinchuk L.S., On Some Peculiarities of Polymer Electric Polarization in Metal 1-Polymer-Metal 2 Systems, High-Mol. Comp., 1988, Vol.30B, No. 6, pp. 427-431.
17. Klimovich A.F. and Guzenkov S.I., Electric Phenomena at Polymer Friction. III, Regularities of Electret State Formation, Soviet Friction and Wear, 1989, Vol. 10, No. 5, pp. 779-785.
18. Voronezhnev Yu.I., Goldade V.A., Pinchuk L.S. and Rechits G.V., Influence of Charge Distribution on Friction Characteristics of Polymer Electret, Soviet J. of Friction and Wear, 1984, Vol. 5, No. 11, pp. 110- 113.
19. USSR Patent No. 1165588, B29C, Device to Manufacture Articles from Polymer Bulk Materials, 1985.
20. USSR Patent No. 1055913, F16C, Sliding-Contact Bearing, 1983.